

eManuSkript: Digital Tools for Palaeography

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Introduction:

Digitised medieval manuscripts are now more accessible than ever, yet the tools needed to analyse them meaningfully remain limited. Traditional palaeography and codicology still rely on specialist training and access to the physical objects. While these methods are fundamental to the field, our approach is to develop tested hands-on tools that offer researchers and institutions easy access, enhance and accelerate existing workflows in manuscript studies, and encourage the exchange of ideas and results. With funding from the *Stiftung Innovation in der Hochschullehre*, the project eManuSkript (April 2024–March 2026) is building an integrated suite of browser-based apps to aid learners and re-

searchers in studying medieval Latin manuscripts. All of the apps are accompanied by tutorials containing text, videos and images that not only introduce the user to traditional palaeography but also illustrate best practices for digital methods. Our goal is to provide both foundational training and advanced analytical tools that make the script, layout, and material aspects of medieval manuscripts more approachable and understandable for both students and researchers in a digital environment.

Methods and Tools:

Proteus

Proteus is a post-processing tool designed to enhance the readability of difficult manuscript texts, such as palimpsests¹ or chemically damaged folios. Proteus makes the use of techniques derived from HOKU (Knox 2022) for multispectral imaging², such as pseudocolour³, principal component analysis⁴, and visible-light enhancements including sharpening, noise reduction, and contrast adjustment (Davies and Zawacki 2020). As a result, faded or removed ink and pigment can reappear through Proteus's processing functions. All image operations are logged with metadata, ensuring reproducibility and shareability. User-provided details about the manuscript and imaging process are saved alongside the enhanced images, making Proteus a valuable tool for scholars working with challenging or layered manuscript materials.

Seshat

Seshat is an interactive tool for script analysis and annotation, designed to examine the micro-features of handwriting in digitized manuscripts. Users can upload images or IIIF links to interact with the script directly, to trace pen strokes, to highlight and underline specific features and to measure angles. Seshat also supports users to measure and annotate stroke angles, stroke thickness, line height and other features directly on the uploaded digital image. By capturing these measurements through user-defined pixel coordinates, Seshat adds a layer of structured, quantifiable data to the manuscript dataset, enhancing its value for both traditional palaeographic study and data-driven analysis. To ensure a traceable workflow and identify errors, all annotations are time-stamped, and user actions are tracked in a viewable document. Users will also be able to generate statistical similarity comparisons of scribal stints to identify individual scribes.

Mergen

We are currently developing an AI-based layout segmentation model to detect key manuscript elements, including text zones, lines, and graphic elements. These have been extensively tested and refined. The model is based on YOLOv10 architecture (Wang et al. 2024) and follows a three-layer detection strategy: zone detection, instance segmentation, and line detection. Training data include harmonised open-source datasets such as CATMuS Medieval (Clérice et al. 2024), YALTAi (Clérice 2022a), MedieYOLOv1 (MedieYOLOv1 Dataset 2025), supplemented by custom and synthetic annotations to improve accuracy. Once complete, the model will enable large-scale structural analysis and support downstream tasks such as script comparison and content extraction.

Fenius

To document the physical appearance of codices, we are currently entering the final phase of designing and programming three bookbinding apps. The applications are designed to support and assist students, scholars and manuscript conservators with understanding, researching and documenting book bindings and bookblock structures. Three apps focus on a different aspect of codicology: One tool provides the main visual interface for modelling bookblock structures, a second tool focuses on sewing patterns, and the third is dedicated to documenting pricking⁵ and ruling⁶ in a schematic representation. The three interactive and customisable interfaces, designed by a professional illustrator working jointly with the team and with the Göttingen State and University Library manuscript conservation department, will enable users to recreate and record bookblock construction, sewing, and pricking/ruling digitally. Since the digital versions usually do not preserve detailed bookbinding information, our tools offer a means of supplementing existing metadata and strengthening codicological research.

Future Directions and Conclusion

All our tools are tested in classroom settings and refined through user feedback. By the end of the project, all applications will be available through our website, and our datasets and backend code will be archived openly on GitHub and Zenodo. Our suite of apps will be further supported by an integrated searchable Zotero library. Beyond providing practical support for learners and researchers, eManuSkript contributes to a growing ecosystem of digital palaeography by promoting interoperability, transparency, and open access. By doing this, we aim to help reshape manuscript research and benefit a new generation of scholars working in a digital environment.

Footnotes

1. Palimpsests: Manuscripts whose original text has been erased so that the parchment can be reused.
2. Multispectral imaging (MSI): Imaging technique that uses various wavelengths of light to retrieve invisible and illegible ink and pigment.
3. Pseudocolour: The digital assignment of artificial colours to highlight differences in different spectral responses.
4. Principal component analysis (PCA): A statistical method used to enhance contrast by separating distinct spectral features.
5. Pricking: Small holes made in the parchment to guide the ruling of the text and margins.
6. Ruling: Lines drawn to organise the page layout before writing.

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